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GDP at Constant Prices in Europe

It grew by an average of 25.4% between 2012 and 2021

Eurostat calculates the value of the GDP trend. The data is given as a percentage. The value is equal to 100 in 2010. Therefore, the changes represent changes in the GDP trend compared to 2010.

Ranking of European countries by value of GDP at market prices in 2021 compared to base year 2010. Ireland ranks first in value of 2021 Gross Domestic Product compared to base year 2010 with a value of 211.45 followed by Turkey with a value of 184.16 and Malta with a value of 169.72. In the middle of the table are Sweden with an amount equal to 124.60 units followed by Slovenia with a value equal to 123.53 and Montenegro with a value equal to 123.50 units. Portugal closes the ranking with a value of 103.42, followed by Italy with a value of 98.00 units and Greece with an amount of 83.91. On average, between 2010 and 2021, European countries increased the value of GDP from a value of 100 up to an amount of 128. However, the countries for which the value of GDP in 2021 was lower than in 2010 are Italy and Greece.

Ranking of European countries by the value of the percentage change in GDP at constant prices with 2010=100 between 2012 and 2021. Ireland is in first place by the value of the percentage change in GDP at constant prices with 2010=100 between 2012 and 2021 with a value equal to 109.71% equal to 110.62 units, followed by Malta with an amount equal to 62.25% equal to 65.12 units, and by Turkey with a value equal to 58.04% equal to an amount of 67.63 units. In the middle of the ranking there are Cyprus with an amount equal to 21.57% equal to an amount of 20.91 units, followed by Sweden with a value equal to 21.45% equal to an amount of 22.01 units and by Bulgaria with a value equal to 21.43% equal to an amount of 22.05 units. The ranking is closed by Spain with a value equal to 7.51% equal to a value of 7.23 units, followed by Greece with an amount of 0.51% equal to an amount of 0.43 units, and by Italy with a value equal to 0.3% equal to an amount of 0.29 units. On average between 2012 and 2021 the value of the percentage change in GDP at constant prices with 2010=100 grew by an amount equal to 24.98%.

Clustering with k-Means algorithm optimized with the Silhouette coefficient. A clustering with k-Means algorithm optimized with the Silhouette coefficient is presented below. In particular, the following clusters are identified, namely:

- Cluster 1: Kosovo, Malta, Turkey, Lithuania, Ireland, Estonia, Poland, Romania, Latvia, Iceland;
- Cluster 2: Hungary, Slovakia, Greece, Luxembourg, North Macedonia, Montenegro, Czech Republic, Sweden, Italy, Cyprus, Portugal, Bosnia, Serbia, Spain, Switzerland, Germany, Bulgaria, Norway, Slovenia, Croatia, Finland, Denmark, France, Austria, Belgium, the Netherlands.

From a strictly geographical point of view, the Baltic countries, Poland, Turkey and the Ukraine are growing more than the rest of Europe.

Network Analysis with Manhattan distance. A network analysis with the distance to Manhattan is presented below. The analysis shows the presence of three complex network structures and three

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simplified network structures. There is a complex network structure between Norway, Germany, Switzerland, Sweden, Luxembourg, North Macedonia, and Slovakia. Particularly:

- Norway has a connection with Germany for a value equal to 0.17 units and with Switzerland for a value equal to 0.19 units;
- Switzerland has a connection with Germany equal to a value of 0.21 units, with Norway equal to a value of 0.19 units and with Sweden equal to an amount of 0.38 units;
- Sweden has a connection with Switzerland equal to an amount of 0.38 units, with Luxembourg equal to an amount of 0.36 units and with North Macedonia for an amount equal to 0.33 units;
- Luxembourg has a connection with Sweden worth 0.36, with Slovakia worth 0.36, and with North Macedonia worth 0.26;
- Slovakia has a connection with Luxembourg equal to 0.36 units and with North Macedonia equal to 0.37 units.

There is a complex network structure between Austria, Belgium and France. In particular, it results that:

- Belgium has a connection with Austria for a value equal to 0.2 units and with France for an amount equal to 0.21 units;
- Austria has a connection with Belgium for a value equal to 0.2 units and with France for a value equal to 0.22 units;
- France has a connection with Austria equal to a value of 0.22 units and with Belgium equal to a value of 0.21 units.

There is a relationship between Bulgaria, Denmark, Serbia, Bosnia and the Czech Republic. In particular:

- Bulgaria has a connection with Denmark worth 0.24 and with Bosnia worth 0.38;
- Bosnia has a connection with Bulgaria for a value equal to 0.38 units, with Denmark for a value equal to 0.29 units and with the Czech Republic for a value equal to 0.35 units;
- The Czech Republic has a connection with Bosnia worth 0.35 units;
- Denmark has a connection with Bulgaria equal to a value of 0.24 units, with Bosnia equal to an amount of 0.29 units and with Serbia equal to an amount of 0.37 units.

There are also simplified network structures, namely:

- Poland has a connection with Romania for a value of 0.22 units;
- Spain has a connection with Croatia worth 0.35 units;
- Estonia has a connection with Lithuania worth 0.34 units.

This network analysis is useful for two reasons:

- It is a representation of how GDP is propagated from one country to another. For example, if GDP increases or decreases in Switzerland then GDP also increases or decreases in Germany, Norway and Sweden. Network analysis therefore represents a set of connections that express the diffusion of GDP trends.
- Can suggest country aggregation methodologies that can confirm or question clustering. For example, the fact that three complex network structures are present could suggest that the clustering model with k-Means algorithm optimized with the Silhouette coefficient is inefficient and therefore should be replaced with other methods such as Elbow's method.

Conclusions. The GDP growth rate grew in the period between 2012 and 2021 however it had a setback between 2019-2020. In fact, between 2019 and 2020 the value of the GDP growth rate decreased by -4.09%. However, between 2020 and 2021 the GDP growth rate calculated at constant prices with 2010=100 grew by 6.81%. It follows that Covid has generated a significant economic loss for European countries. However, regardless of the covid effect, which in any case ended in the 2019-2020 financial year, it is possible to verify an enormous divergence between European countries in terms of GDP growth rate. Indeed, there is great heterogeneity in GDP trends across countries. For example, comparing the performance of Ireland's GDP with that of Greece between 2012 and 2021 it appears that while Ireland has more than doubled its GDP at constant prices, Greece has increased its GDP at constant prices only by 5%, remaining in any case below the value of the reference year, i.e. 2010. It therefore follows that although there is a generalized trend in economic growth, not all countries grow, and some even fail to even reach the value of the 2010 GDP considered as the base year. In this sense, greater coordination of European economic policies is needed to ensure that there is convergence between European countries. In fact, if the trends continue to be divergent then an inequality could be created between European countries which could question the usefulness of the institutions of the Union in promoting and defending the interests of the peoples and nations of Europe.

Declarations

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Appendix

Ranking dei paesi europei per valore del PIL a prezzi costanti (2010=100) nel 2021					
Rank	Country	2021	Rank	Country	2021
1	<i>Ireland</i>	211,45	19	<i>Montenegro</i>	123,50
2	<i>Türkiye</i>	184,16	20	<i>North Macedonia</i>	122,42
3	<i>Malta</i>	169,72	21	<i>Czechia</i>	122,04
4	<i>Kosovo</i>	156,71	22	<i>Denmark</i>	120,40
5	<i>Estonia</i>	148,76	23	<i>Switzerland</i>	119,47
6	<i>Lithuania</i>	148,45	24	<i>Norway</i>	118,39
7	<i>Poland</i>	146,22	25	<i>Cyprus</i>	117,87
8	<i>Romania</i>	142,34	26	<i>Croatia</i>	116,78
9	<i>Latvia</i>	136,13	27	<i>Germany</i>	115,11
10	<i>Hungary</i>	133,26	28	<i>Netherlands</i>	114,82
11	<i>Iceland</i>	132,26	29	<i>Belgium</i>	114,76
12	<i>Serbia</i>	128,07	30	<i>Austria</i>	111,79
13	<i>Luxembourg</i>	127,74	31	<i>France</i>	111,22
14	<i>Slovakia</i>	125,95	32	<i>Finland</i>	109,80
15	<i>Bosnia and Herzegovina</i>	125,89	33	<i>Spain</i>	103,48
16	<i>Bulgaria</i>	124,92	34	<i>Portugal</i>	103,42
17	<i>Sweden</i>	124,60	35	<i>Italy</i>	98,00
18	<i>Slovenia</i>	123,53	36	<i>Greece</i>	83,91

C1>C2

■ C1

■ C2

